

ISic4389

terminus marker?

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

terminus

Material

sandstone

Object

block

Editor

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Autopsy

2016-06-27

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance

Part of the initial museum collection, without date of acquisition, noted by Orsi (Taccuino 1, p.78) as from Cantera, i.e. Megara Hyblaea

Coordinates

37.203699, 15.181796

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 223

Physical Description

A block of yellow-orange local sandstone ('tufo arenaria'), intact left and below, but seemingly broken on top and on the right. Roughly finished on the reverse.

Dimensions

Height 33 cm

Width 48 cm

Depth 10 cm

Layout

Two lines of Greek text, with a deep horizontal line above each (same depth as the letters). Although the stone is broken top and right, there is no clear evidence that the text continued beyond what is preserved (the surface is preserved beyond the text, and the 'guidelines' also stop with the preserved text. A cross precedes line 1.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Deeply and neatly cut letters (given the material). Xsi formed by multiple straight strokes, alternately horizontal and diagonal; epsilon has equal length bars; Nu has the diagonal not reaching to either top or bottom of the vertical strokes; beta is closed, with lower eye larger than upper; alpha has an extended upper serif, and crossbar is oblique, descending to left; sigma is lunate; kappa has full length arms.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 70-75 mm

Line 2: 60-70 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 20-30 mm

Text

1. □ ΕΕΝ

2. ΒΑΣΛΚ

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Commentary

This stone is a second example of a text known and published from Megara Hyblaea, found in 1965 and published by Manni Piraino in 1975 (ISic3698 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3698>]). This example, although clearly found before 1888, as on display in the 'sala cristiana' of the original museum in Siracusa, and noted by Orsi in his first 'taccuino', remains formally unpublished. Its interpretation remains uncertain, but given the existence of two such stones, some form of property or boundary marker, perhaps in relation to church land, seems most likely.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Tréziny, Henry 2018. Mégara Hyblaea. 7, La ville classique, hellénistique et romaine. *CEFR*. Rome. At 275

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Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014